

Boundary Geometrodynamics of Gauge Interaction

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(Dated: November 9, 2011)

The paper is devoted to a possible geometrodynamical interpretation of gauge invariance in terms of the formalism of field theory in compact space-time dimensions [1]. In this formalism, the kinematical information of an interacting elementary particle is encoded on the relativistic geometrodynamics of the boundary of the theory through local transformations of the underlying space-time coordinates. Gauge interactions are described as invariance of the theory under local deformations of the boundary. The resulting local variations of the field solution are interpreted as internal transformations, and the internal symmetries of the gauge theory turn out to be related to corresponding space-time local symmetries. In the approximation of local infinitesimal isometric transformations, Maxwell's kinematics and gauge invariance are inferred directly from the variational principle. Furthermore we explicitly impose periodic conditions at the boundary of the theory as semi-classical quantization condition in order to investigate the quantum behavior of gauge interaction. In the abelian case the result is a remarkable correspondence with scalar QED.

INTRODUCTION

In 1918 Weyl [2] introduced the idea of gauge invariance in field theory in an attempt to describe electromagnetic interaction as invariance under local transformations of space-time coordinates. In particular he tried to extend the principle of relativity of the choice of reference frame to the choice of local units of length. For this reason the idea was named *gauge* invariance. The requirement of gauge invariance in fact necessitates the introduction of a new field in the theory, named the *compensating* field [3]. It cancels all the unwanted effects of the local transformations of variables such as the related *internal transformation* of the matter fields, and enable the existence of a local symmetry. Weyl noticed that such a compensating field has important analogies with the electromagnetic potential. His proposal was very appealing because of its deep analogies with the geometrodynamical description of General Relativity (GR). Even though the compensating field associated with local Weyl transformations can be successfully used to represent gravitational interactions, further developments soon showed that such geometrodynamical description of electromagnetism (EM) was not possible. Contrary to the experimental evidence, the compensating field associated with Weyl's gauge interacts in the same manner with particle and antiparticles. The possibility of a geometrodynamical description of EM in terms of local transformations of the underlying space-time coordinates was abandoned, though the terms gauge invariance still remain for historical reasons. In order to reproduce the correct gauge field (*i.e.* compensating fields with an imaginary unit in front with respect to the original Weyl compensating fields) a symmetry under local phase transformations of the matter fields was postulated. These *internal transformations* of the fields originate ordinary gauge interaction.

Another important attempt for a geometrodynamical description of gauge interaction is represented by the so-called Kaluza's miracle. In [4] Kaluza showed that classical EM actually has a well defined geometrodynamical

interpretation, but this interpretation involves an eXtra-Dimension (XD) — at least as a “mathematical trick”. The gauge field appears as entries in the space-time components on XD Kaluza's metric and the Maxwell equations are retrieved from the fifth components of the five-dimensional (5D) Einstein equations. This represent a *de facto* 5D geometrodynamical unification of electromagnetic and gravitational interaction. Also to be considered is Klein's original proposal, which was to impose Periodic Boundary Conditions (PBCs) at the ends of a compact XD (cyclic XD with topology S^1) in the attempt of a semiclassical interpretation of Quantum Mechanics (QM). In [5] he actually noticed that such PBCs provide an analogy with the Bohr-Sommerfeld quantization condition — in particular he used this hypothetical cyclic XD to interpret the quantization of the electric charge.

In this paper we will investigate these attempts for a geometrodynamical description of gauge invariance in terms of the formalism of field theory in compact space-time dimensions (compact 4D). This formalism, defined in [1] and summarized in sec.(I), see also [6–10], can be regarded as the natural realization of the de Broglie assumption at the base of wave mechanics (wave-particle duality). By using de Broglie's words, the formalism is based on the fundamental assumption “*of existence of a certain periodic phenomenon of a yet to be determined character, which is to be attributed to each and every isolated energy parcel [elementary particle]*” [11, 12]. This so-called “de Broglie periodic phenomenon” [13] or “de Broglie internal clock” [14] has been implicitly tested by 80 years of QFT and indirectly observed in a recent experiment [14]. We will realize this assumption by imposing the de Broglie periodicity as a constrain to a free field. That is to say, as the solution of a bosonic action in compact 4D and PBCs. This means that the compactification lengths as well as the boundary of the theory, are explicitly related to the de Broglie periodicity. Therefore the resulting field solution will be a sum over harmonic modes similarly to a string vibrating in compact dimensions. That is, the PBCs (allowed by the variational prin-

principle) will be used as quantization condition similarly to the semi-classical quantization of a particle in a box.

In the first part of the paper we will mainly investigate classical gauge invariance, in particular classical EM. In par.(II), we will investigate in a geometrical way how the de Broglie spatial and temporal periodicities of an elementary boson, *i.e.* of a corresponding single mode of a Klein-Gordon (KG) field, varies dynamically under local transformations of reference frame or interactions. The temporal and spatial de Broglie periodicities can be used to describe the four-momentum of a particle, according to the de Broglie phase harmony. They can be represented as a four-vector. Such a de Broglie four-periodicity is derived by Lorentz transformations from the invariant periodicity of the proper time associated with the mass of the particle. Indeed it describes a “periodic phenomenon” of topology S^1 . According to de Broglie, the local and retarded variations of four-momentum (or four-frequency) of a particle occurring during a given relativistic interaction scheme can be equivalently described in terms of local and retarded variations of four-periodicity of a corresponding periodic phenomenon. In the formalism of field theory in compact 4D the de Broglie four-periodicity are described by the boundary of the theory. Thus the kinematics of a particle in a given interaction scheme turns out to be encoded in corresponding geometrodynamics of the boundary of the theory — in a manner of a holographic principle. Furthermore, deformations of the boundary of the action can be obtained from corresponding transformations of the space-time variables, *i.e.* diffeomorphisms of the compact 4D of the theory. Hence this description of interaction mimics linearized gravity. In fact gravitational interaction can be described in terms of variations of periodicity of reference clocks encoded in corresponding geometrodynamics of the underlying 4D. In [16] we have noticed that such a geometrodynamical description applied to the Quark-Gluon-Plasma (QGP) exponential freeze-out actually provide an interesting parallelism with phenomenological aspects of the AdS/QCD correspondence.

Thus, similarly to GR, we want to describe interaction in terms of invariance of the theory under a corresponding local transformations of variables. In ordinary field theory simple isometric transformations of the underlying space-time dimensions have no effect. This is essentially because in ordinary field theory the BCs have a very marginal role. The KG field used for practical computations is the most generic solution of the KG equation. However, as evident in our formalism, a generic transformation of variables implies a corresponding deformation of the boundary of the theory and in turn, through the PBCs, of the de Broglie periodicity of the field solution of the theory. Thus we have a variation of field solutions even in the case in which the transformation of variables is a simple isometry. In fact, even if the transformation is from a flat space-time to a flat space-time, leaving the structure of the action invariant, it could involve a corresponding deformation (rotation) of the boundary of the

theory. We will show that classical gauge interactions can be derived by requiring invariance of the theory in compact 4D under local isometries and by applying the variational principle at the boundary. In this paper we limit our study to the approximation of local isometries; that is, particular isomorphisms where the lengths of the four-vectors are in a first approximation preserved (contrary to the Weyl invariance we do not consider scale transformations). The case of local scale (conformal) invariance has been partially investigated in [16] through the dualism with XD theories. More in detail, in sec.(III) we will interpret the variation of the field solution associated to a local isometry in terms of internal symmetries of the field. A local isometry induces a minimal substitution formally equivalent to classical EM. From the variational principle it is possible to find out that this description formally reproduces the Noether current of ordinary gauge interactions. The symmetry of the gauge transformation turns out to be the symmetry of the isometry which originates it. The resulting gauge field describes the local deformation of periodicity of a matter field under a local transformation of variables. In sec.(IV), we will find that the only possible way to write fields with different periodicities in an action with persistent boundary is to write gauge invariant terms. The requirement of gauge invariance is therefore derived from the variational principle. Gauge transformations allows one to tune the periodicity of the different fields of a theory in order to minimize the action at the common boundary. For the same reason we will see that only particular types of local isometries, which we will call *polarized*, are allowed by the variational principle. These polarized local isometries reproduce Maxwell dynamics for the gauge field. Thus the geometrodynamics associated with these particular local isometries reproduce formally classical gauge theory. In [16] we have shown that field theory in compact 4D is dual to the Kaluza-Klein (KK) field theory. Under this dualism the geometrodynamics description of gauge interaction proposed here can be regarded as a purely 4D formulation of Kaluza’s original proposal.

The formalism of field theory in compact 4D also provides an interesting analogy with Klein’s original proposal. In fact, in [1, 16] we have shown that the PBCs at the geometrodynamical boundary of the theory represent a semi-classical quantization condition. This can be regarded as the relativistic generalization of the quantization of a particle in a box. The Feynman Path Integral (FPI) formulation arises in a semi-classical way as interference between classical paths with different winding numbers associated with the underlying cyclic geometry S^1 of the compact 4D [1, 6]. Moreover the theory has implicit commutation relations. Generalizing this description, in sec.(V) we will finally find that the variation of four-periodicity of an interacting cyclic field is formally described in local Hilbert spaces by the ordinary Scattering Matrix of QM. The space-time evolution associated to such local isometries of the compact 4D is formally described by the ordinary FPI of scalar QED.

I. COMPACT SPACE-TIME FORMALISM

In relativistic mechanics every isolated elementary system (free elementary particle) has associated persistent four-momentum $\bar{p}_\mu = \{\bar{E}/c, -\bar{\mathbf{p}}\}$. On the other hand, the de Broglie-Planck formulation of QM prescribes that to every particle with four-momentum there is a corresponding “periodic phenomenon” with four-angular-frequency $\bar{\omega}_\mu = \bar{p}_\mu c/\hbar$, *i.e.* with corresponding de Broglie four-periodicity $T^\mu = \{T_t, \vec{\lambda}_x/c\}$. The topology of this so-called “de Broglie periodic phenomenon” is \mathbb{S}^1 . In fact it is fully characterized by the proper time periodicity T_τ [11, 12]. In a generic frame, the spatial and temporal components of the de Broglie four-periodicity T^μ are obtained through Lorentz transformations: $cT_\tau = c\gamma T_t - \gamma\vec{\beta} \cdot \vec{\lambda}_x$. The energy and the momentum of a particle with mass \bar{M} in the new reference frame is $E = \gamma\bar{M}c^2$ and $\bar{\mathbf{p}} = \gamma\vec{\beta}\bar{M}c$, respectively. In the “de Broglie periodic phenomenon” the proper time periodicity is fixed by the mass of the particle, according to $T_\tau\bar{M}c^2 = h$. Therefore, in a generic reference frame, we have de Broglie-Planck relation (de Broglie phase harmony)

$$c\bar{p}_\mu T^\mu = h. \quad (1)$$

Similarly to the de Broglie assumption of “periodic phenomenon”, in the compact 4D formalism [1] we assume that with every elementary bosonic particle with four-momentum \bar{p}_μ is associated an intrinsically periodic bosonic field whose de Broglie four-periodicity T^μ is fixed dynamically through PBCs. (1). This means that, as long as we describe free particles, *i.e.* persistent \bar{p}_μ , the intrinsic four-periodicity T^μ of the fields must be assumed to be persistent. Thus we describe such a free bosonic field with persistent four-periodicity T^μ as the field solution of a relativistic bosonic action in compact 4D with PBCs (represented by the circle in the volume integral \oint)

$$\mathcal{S} = \oint_0^{T^\mu} d^4x \mathcal{L}(\partial_\mu \Phi(x), \Phi(x)). \quad (2)$$

Roughly speaking, in the “de Broglie internal clock” the whole physical information is contained in a single four-period T^μ , [1] [20].

It is important to note that the PBCs minimize the above bosonic action at the boundary. That is, every bosonic field (solution of the Euler-Lagrange equations) with four-periodicity T^μ automatically minimizes the above action [1]. This is the fundamental reason why the theory turns out to be fully consistent with Special Relativity (SR) [1]. Indeed PBCs have the same formal validity of the usual Stationary (or Synchronous) BCs (SBCs) of ordinary field theory (*i.e.* fixed values of the fields at the boundary). The Lorentz covariance of relativistic actions is preserved by PBCs.

The theory satisfies time ordering and relativistic causality. In fact, just as Newton’s law of inertia doesn’t

imply that every point particle moves on a straight line (persistent \bar{p}_μ), our assumption of intrinsic periodicities does not mean that our field solutions have always persistent periodicities T^μ . Indeed, the four-periodicity T^μ must be regarded as local and dynamical as the four-momentum \bar{p}_μ , according to (1). The retarded and local variations of four-momentum occurring during interactions imply retarded and local variations of the intrinsic four-periodicity of the particles. Events in time are characterized by variations of periodic regimes of the fields. In this theory we must interpret relativistic causality and time ordering in terms of variations of four-periodicity rather than of variations of four-momentum (roughly speaking, they are two faces of the same coin).

To see explicitly that the theory is Lorentz invariant we consider a global Lorentz transformation

$$x^\mu \rightarrow x'^\mu = \Lambda_\nu^\mu x^\nu \quad (3)$$

as a global and isometric substitution of variables in the action (2). The resulting action

$$\mathcal{S} = \oint_0^{T'^\mu} d^4x' \mathcal{L}(\partial'_\mu \Phi'(x'), \Phi'(x')) \quad (4)$$

describes the same elementary system of (2) but in a new reference frame. It is important to note that, even though we are considering an isometry and the form of the bosonic Lagrangian is unchanged, the transformation of variables induces a correspondent transformation (rotation) of the boundary of the theory

$$T^\mu \rightarrow T'^\mu = \Lambda_\nu^\mu T^\nu. \quad (5)$$

Indeed we find that T^μ — being an ordinary space-time interval — transforms as a contravariant four-vector.

This implies that the field solution $\Phi'(x')$ minimizing the transformed action (4) is in general different from the field solution $\Phi(x)$ of the free original action (2). They have the same equations of motion but they have different BCs. This aspect will play a central role in the rest of the paper. Besides the naive substitution of the 4D variable $x \rightarrow x'$, to minimize the transformed action (4), the transformed field solution $\Phi'(x')$ must have transformed de Broglie four-periodicity T'^μ . Thus, according to (1), the transformed four-momentum associated with the transformed field $\Phi'(x')$ is

$$\bar{p}_\mu \rightarrow \bar{p}'_\mu = \Lambda_\nu^\mu \bar{p}_\nu. \quad (6)$$

This actually describes the four-momentum of our elementary particle in the new reference system, as expected from the Lorentz transformation (3). The de Broglie phase harmony (1) prescribes that T^μ is such that the phase of the field is invariant under four-periodic translations. But the phase of the field is also invariant (scalar) under transformation of variables. Thus

$$e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar}x^\mu\bar{p}_\mu} = e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar}(x^\mu+cT^\mu)\bar{p}_\mu} \rightarrow e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar}(x'^\mu+cT'^\mu)\bar{p}'_\mu} = e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar}x'^\mu\bar{p}'_\mu}.$$

The intrinsic four-periodicity of the field transforms from reference frame to reference frame in a relativistic way as in (5). This description is equivalent to the relativistic Doppler effect. By using the useful notation $\bar{p}_\mu = h/T^\mu c$ [15] the relativistic constrain on the variations of the temporal and spatial components of the de Broglie periodicity can be expressed as

$$\frac{1}{T_\tau^2} \equiv \frac{1}{T_\mu} \frac{1}{T^\mu}. \quad (7)$$

This constrain is induced by the underlying Minkowski metric $c^2 d\tau^2 = dx^\mu dx_\mu$. In fact, if multiplied by the Planck constant, (7) is nothing but the geometrical description in terms of four-periodicity of the relativistic constraint

$$\bar{M}^2 c^2 = \bar{p}^\mu \bar{p}_\mu, \quad (8)$$

in agreement with (1). The mass \bar{M} is described by the proper time periodicity T_τ of the field: $\bar{M} = h/T_\tau c^2$. This corresponds to the time for light to travel across the Compton wavelength of the elementary system $\lambda_s = cT_\tau$. A massless elementary system has infinite (or frozen) proper time periodicity. A hypothetical bosonic particle with the mass of an electron has proper time periodicity of the order of $\sim 10^{-20} s$. This is extremely fast even if compared with the modern resolution in time which is of the order of $\sim 10^{-17} s$, or with the characteristic periodicity of the Cesium atom which by definition is $\sim 10^{-10} s$.

The geometrical constraint (7) describes the relativistic dispersion relation of the energy of our elementary system

$$\bar{E}(\bar{\mathbf{p}}) = \sqrt{\bar{\mathbf{p}}^2 c^2 + \bar{M}^2 c^4}. \quad (9)$$

In the first part of the paper we will consider only the fundamental field solution $\bar{\Phi}(x)$ of the action in compact 4D (2). This is the single mode of de Broglie four-angular-frequency $\bar{\omega}_\mu$ associated with the PBCs at the boundary T^μ . We use the normalization of a string vibrating in compact 4D (similar to the case of ‘‘a particle in a box’’), so that \bar{N} depends only on the volume of the compact 4D and is invariant under isometries. We will denote by the bar sign the quantities related to the fundamental mode of a cyclic field. That is

$$\bar{\Phi}(x) = \bar{N} \bar{\phi}(x) = \bar{N} e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar} \bar{p}_\mu x^\mu}. \quad (10)$$

As we will see in more explicitly in sec.(V), this fundamental mode corresponds to the non-quantum (tree-level) limit of the theory. Since its dispersion relation is (9), it describes the relativistic behavior of a corresponding classical particle with mass \bar{M} . In fact, the fundamental solution $\bar{\Phi}(x)$, extended to the whole Minkowskian space-time \mathbb{R}^4 , formally corresponds to a single mode of an ordinary non-quantized free Klein-Gordon (KG) field $\Phi_{KG}(x) = \bar{\Phi}(x)$ with same mass $M_{KG} = \bar{M}$ and energy $E_{KG}(\bar{\mathbf{p}}) = \bar{E}(\bar{\mathbf{p}})$. In other words, they have the same four-momentum \bar{p}_μ , four periodicity

T^μ and dispersion relation (9). The fundamental mode, as a single non-quantized KG mode, can be use to describe a classical particle. Thus, in terms of the invariant mass \bar{M} , the fundamental mode $\bar{\Phi}(x)$ is described by the following action in compact 4D

$$\bar{S} = \frac{1}{2} \int^{T^\mu} d^4x [\partial_\mu \bar{\Phi}^*(x) \partial^\mu \bar{\Phi}(x) - \bar{M}^2 \bar{\Phi}^*(x) \bar{\Phi}(x)] \quad (11)$$

This action is formally the KG action with boundary T^μ . In this case the PBCs are replaced by suitable SBCs in order to select the single fundamental mode with persistent four-periodicity T^μ — we have eliminated the circle from the integral symbol in order to distinguish its solution from more general field solution of the action with PBCs. As we will see in sec.(II A 1), the study of the variations of BCs proposed here for field theory in compact 4D can be extended to the SBCs of ordinary field theory.

When in the last part of the paper we will investigate the quantum behavior of the theory, we will need to use the most generic field solution with intrinsic four-periodicity T^μ . We will address this generic solution as cyclic field. Similarly to a vibrating string or a particle in a box it is easy to figure out that such a generic cyclic field solution (topology S^1) will be a sum of the eigenmodes associated with a quantized energy-momentum spectrum.

II. TOWARDS INTERACTION

According to the de Broglie-Planck relation (1) the local and retarded variation four-momentum occurring during interactions can be equivalently written as a local and retarded variation of de Broglie four-periodicity. In GR, variations of periodicity of the reference clocks are expressed in terms of deformations of the underlying 4D. Similarly we will describe the variation of periodicity of the cyclic fields during interaction in terms of geometrodynamics in curved 4D.

A. Geometrodynamics

In relativistic mechanics a generic interaction scheme can be formalized in terms of corresponding variations of the four-momentum $\bar{p}'_\mu(x)$ with respect to the non interacting case \bar{p}_μ . That is,

$$\bar{p}_\mu \rightarrow \bar{p}'_\mu(x) = e^a_\mu(x) \bar{p}_a. \quad (12)$$

With this notation we mean that the persistent four-momentum \bar{p}_μ in any given interaction point $x = X$ deforms into $\bar{p}'_\mu(x)|_{x=X}$ when we switch on interaction. Hence the interaction scheme (12) is locally encoded by the tetrad $e^a_\mu(x)$.

Similarly to GR where interaction is encoded in a corresponding deformation of the underlying 4D, we will formalize interactions in terms of local diffeomorphisms of

the compact 4D. This means that we will generalize the case of global transformation of variable (3) to the case of local transformations. We will therefore use field theory in curved 4D.

To describe this interaction scheme in terms of cyclic fields we must apply the de Broglie-Planck condition (1) locally. It must be noted however that when interaction are concerned, the local four-periodicity of the interacting field which we will denote from now on by $\tau'^{\mu}(x)$, in general does not coincide with the boundary of the theory at $T^{\mu}(x)$. That is, in general $\tau'^{\mu}(x) \neq T^{\mu}(x)$. As we will see, $T^{\mu}(x)$ transforms as a finite and contravariant four-vector, *i.e.* as x'^{μ} , whereas $\tau'^{\mu}(x)$ transforms as a tangent [15] and contravariant four-vector, *i.e.* as dx'^{μ} (the former describes the recurrence period $\Phi'(x) = \Phi'(x+T)$ whereas the latter describes periodicity in a given point). The periodicity $\tau'^{\mu}(x)$ of an interacting field varies from point to point, according to the relativistic retarded potentials. In this case the local de Broglie phase harmony is

$$c\bar{p}'_{\mu}(x)\tau'^{\mu}(x) = h. \quad (13)$$

Therefore the local variation of four-momentum in the interaction scheme (12) corresponds to the contravariant local variation of the four-periodicity

$$T^{\mu} \rightarrow \tau'^{\mu}(x) = T^a e_a^{\mu}(x). \quad (14)$$

Similarly to the variation of four-momentum induced by a given interaction scheme with respect to the free case, the persistent four-periodicity $T^{\mu} = \tau^{\mu}$ of the free field $\Phi(x)$ turns out to be the local four-periodicity $\tau'^{\mu}(x)$ for the interacting field $\Phi'(x)$.

The deformation of the local four-periodicity $\tau'^{\mu}(x)$ of the cyclic fields is associated with the corresponding stretching of the compactification four-vector $T'^{\mu}(x)$ of the theory through the PBCs. This actually induces a deformation of the original Minkowskian metric according to the following relation

$$\eta_{\mu\nu} \rightarrow g_{\mu\nu}(x) = e_a^{\alpha}(x)e_{\nu}^b(x)\eta_{ab}. \quad (15)$$

This resulting curved space-time encodes the interaction scheme (12) locally. To check this geometrodynamical description we consider a local transformation of variables

$$x^{\mu} \rightarrow x'^{\mu}(x) = x^a \Lambda_a^{\mu}(x), \quad (16)$$

whose tetrad matches the one used in (13) to encode our interaction scheme. That is

$$e_a^{\mu}(X) = \left(\frac{\partial x^{\mu}}{\partial x'^a} \right)_{x'=X}. \quad (17)$$

For the scope of this paper we will work in the approximation $e_a^{\mu}(x') \simeq e_a^{\mu}(x)$ (for the sake of simplicity we neglect Christoffel symbols). Since $x^a \Lambda_a^{\mu}(x)$ is the primitive of the tetrad $e_a^{\mu}(x)$ we can use the following notation

(omitting prime indexes in the integrands)

$$x^a \Lambda_a^{\mu}(x) \simeq \int^{x^a} dx^a e_a^{\mu}(x). \quad (18)$$

The transformation (16) relates locally the inertial frame $x \in \mathcal{S}$ of the free cyclic field solution $\Phi(x)$ to the generic frame $x' \in \mathcal{S}'$ associated with the interacting cyclic field solution $\Phi'(x)$. Its Jacobian is $\sqrt{-g(x)} = \det[e_a^{\mu}(x)]$. The Latin letters describe the free field in an inertial frame S while the Greek letters refer to the locally accelerated frame S' of the interacting field Φ' [17]. Finally, by using (16) as a substitution of variables in the compact 4D action (2), we find that the interaction scheme (12) is described by the following action in deformed compact 4D

$$\mathcal{S} \simeq \oint^{T^a \Lambda_a^{\mu}|_X(T)} d^4x \sqrt{-g(x)} \mathcal{L}(e_a^{\mu}(x) \partial_{\mu} \Phi'(x), \Phi'(x)). \quad (19)$$

It is important to point out that (16) induces the local deformation (or stretching) of the compactification four-vector

$$T'^{\mu}(X) \simeq T^a \Lambda_a^{\mu}|_X(T) \simeq \int_{X^a}^{X^a+T^a} dx^a e_a^{\mu}(x). \quad (20)$$

This is the local deformation of the boundary associated with the variation of local periodicity $\tau'^{\mu}(x)$ (14), *i.e.* with the interaction scheme (12).

Indeed our interacting system is described by the cyclic field solution $\Phi'(x)$ of the transformed action (19) in curved space-time (15). According to the diffeomorphism (16) or to the phase harmony (13), if the free cyclic field $\Phi(x)$ has four-momentum p_{μ} , the transformed cyclic field $\Phi'(x)$ has corresponding four-momentum $\bar{p}'_{\mu}(x)$. The four-momentum of the field is in fact described by the derivative operator ∂_{μ} which transforms as the tangent four vector $\bar{p}'_{\mu}(x)$, *i.e.* $\partial_{\mu} \rightarrow \partial'_{\mu} = e_a^{\mu}(x) \partial_a$.

The explicit form of the cyclic field solution $\Phi'(x)$ will be written later for the particular transformations where the normalization $\bar{\mathcal{N}}$ is left invariant. To study the tree-level behavior of the system under the generic interaction scheme (12) in this first part of the paper will be sufficient to consider only the fundamental modes $\bar{\Phi}'(x)$. Similarly to (11), its interaction is described by the transformed action

$$\bar{\mathcal{S}} \simeq \int^{T^a \Lambda_a^{\mu}|_X(T)} d^4x \sqrt{-g(x)} \bar{\mathcal{L}}(e_a^{\mu}(x) \partial_{\mu} \bar{\Phi}'(x), \bar{\Phi}'(x)). \quad (21)$$

This is formally the KG action in curved space-time $g_{\mu\nu}(x)$ with finite integration region $T'^{\mu}(X)$ and suitable SBCs to select $\bar{\Phi}'(x)$ as solution.

1. Generalization to ordinary field theory

In the practical applications of ordinary field theory the role of the BCs is marginal. The ordinary fields used

for computations are the more generic solution of the KG equation, *i.e.* an integral over all the possible energy eigenmodes. In this paper we will see that the formalism of fields in compact 4D has interesting properties that are not manifest in ordinary field theory. The variation of the boundary of the action describes different field solutions, and in turns different kinematic configurations of the same particles. The action (21) actually allows one to investigate the dynamical behavior of a single KG mode under transformations of reference frame. Its variation of four-momentum $\bar{p}'_\mu(x)$, *i.e.* its kinematics, is therefore encoded in the deformation of the boundary, in a manner of a holographic principle.

Although in ordinary field theory BCs are not explicitly used in practical computations, a boundary Σ^μ is implicitly assumed (typically of infinite spatial lengths). Suitable SBCs at Σ^μ can also be applied to ordinary KG action in order to select a particular single mode which locally matches a KG mode: $\bar{\Phi}'(x)|_{x=X} \equiv \bar{\Phi}_{KG}(X)$. The generalization to the ordinary field theory with generic boundary Σ^μ and suitable SBCs is formally obtained from (2) through the following formal substitution $\oint^{T^\mu} \rightarrow \int^{\Sigma^\mu}$ [18]. By analogy to field theory in compact 4D, through the transformation of variable (16) it is easy to find that — in the approximation used in this paper — this generic integration region $\Sigma^\mu(x)$ transforms as (20). That is $\Sigma^\mu \rightarrow \Sigma'^\mu(X) \sim \Sigma^a \Lambda_a^\mu|_X(\Sigma)$. With this we wanted to point out that the analysis of gauge interactions that we will carry on in the next sections for the fundamental mode, can be extended to single modes of ordinary non-quantized KG fields.

B. Applications

We have introduced interactions for cyclic fields in terms of the local diffeomorphisms (16) from a flat manifold S to a generic manifold S' . Thus our system under the interaction scheme (12) is described in terms of the geometrodynamics of the compact 4D.

In order to illustrate this in a heuristic way, we will briefly discuss two examples: the weak Newtonian interaction and the Quark-Gluon-Plasma logarithmic freeze-out. The complete analysis of the former case will be left to forthcoming papers whereas the case of the Quark-Gluon-Plasma has been investigated in [16]. In this preliminary section we will work in the approximation in which the local four-periodicity can be identified with the compactification four-vector of the theory $\tau^\mu(x) \sim T^\mu(x)$. This approximation is valid in the cases where the metric varies sufficiently smoothly, *i.e.* $e_\mu^a(x) \sim \Lambda_\mu^a(x)$.

In the next section, by writing (12) as a minimal substitution, we will show that such a geometrodynamical approach to interactions can be also used to describe gauge interactions.

1. Weak Newtonian potential

The geometrodynamical approach to interactions is interesting because it actually mimics the usual geometrodynamical approach of linearized gravity. To show this we consider a weak Newtonian potential $V(\mathbf{x}) = -GM_\odot/|\mathbf{x}| \ll c^2$. Under this interaction scheme the energy in a gravitational well varies with respect to the free case as $\bar{E} \rightarrow \bar{E}' \sim (1 + GM_\odot/|\mathbf{x}|c^2) \bar{E}$, [19]. According to the geometrodynamical description of interaction (14), this means that the de Broglie clocks in a gravitational well (the periodicity of cyclic fields) are slower with respect to the free clocks $T_t \rightarrow \tau'_t \sim (1 - GM_\odot/|\mathbf{x}|c^2) T_t$. With the schematization of interactions based on the de Broglie phase harmony (1), we have retrieved two important predictions of GR such as time dilatation and gravitational red-shift $\bar{\omega} \rightarrow \bar{\omega}' \sim (1 + GM_\odot/|\mathbf{x}|c^2) \bar{\omega}$.

Besides this we may also consider the analogous variation of spatial momentum and the corresponding variation of spatial periodicities of cyclic fields in a gravitational well [19]. Thus, according to (15), we find that the weak Newtonian interaction turns out to be encoded in the linearized Schwarzschild metric.

Indeed, the geometrodynamical description of interaction in the formalism of compact 4D actually mimics linearized gravity. In the formalism of compact 4D every cyclic field can be regarded as a relativistic reference clock [20], namely the “de Broglie internal clock”. The diffeomorphism (16) encodes the variation of periodicity of this clocks occurring during interaction. This is similar to GR where gravitational interaction can be interpreted in terms of variations of periodicity of reference clocks encoded in a corresponding deformed 4D background. Furthermore, it is well known that GR can be derived from the linearized formulation by considering self-interactions [19] — for instance by relaxing the assumption of smooth interactions. Nevertheless it is important to mention that is not uniquely defined “what is fixed at the boundary of the action principle of GR” [22]. Further considerations about this aspect has been given in [9, 10]. SR and GR fix the differential framework of the 4D without giving any particular prescription about the BCs. The only requirement for the BCs is to minimize a relativistic action at the boundary. For this aspect both SBCs and PBCs have the same formal validity and consistence with relativity. With this analysis we have provided an evidence of the consistence of our formalism of compact 4D with GR.

2. AdS/CFT interpretation

In [16] we have applied the geometrodynamical description of interaction in compact 4D to a simple Bjorken Hydrodynamical Model for Quark-Gluon-Plasma (QGP) logarithmic freeze-out [23]. In a first approximation the fields constituting the QGP can be supposed massless and their four-momentum can be supposed to de-

cay exponentially during the freeze-out. According to (12), this interaction scheme is therefore encoded by the conformal warped tetrad $e_\mu^a(|x|) = \delta_\mu^a e^{-k|x|/c}$, where $|x|/c = s/c = \tau$ and k are the proper time and the gradient of the QGP freeze-out, respectively. The time periodicity $T_t(s) = e^{ks}/k = h/E(s)$ is the conformal parameter which describes naturally the inverse energy of the fields during the freeze-out, according to de Broglie. The resulting variations of normalization of the cyclic field solutions during the freeze-out reproduce formally the logarithmic running of the coupling constant typical of QCD [16]. In this paper we will not explore further the running associated with gauge interactions. This means that we will limit our investigation to transformations of variables which (in a first approximation) preserve the lengths.

Moreover, in [16] we have also shown that a field in deformed compact 4D is dual to a massless XD field in a corresponding 5D metric. For instance they have the same topology \mathbb{S}^1 . The dualism is explicit if we assume that our cyclic world-line parameter plays the role of a cyclic XD. To address this identification we say that the theory has a *virtual* XD, see also [1]. In the formalism of a *virtual* XD, the QGP exponential freeze-out turns out to be encoded in a *virtual* AdS metric and the classical configurations of cyclic fields in such a deformed background reproduces basic aspects of AdS/QCD.

III. ROTATING THE BOUNDARY

In the particular case of local isometries, only the boundary of the theory is deformed without affecting the underlying flat metric. The coefficients of these local isometries can be described in terms of vectorial fields which therefore encode the transformation. The resulting variation of four-momentum and four-periodicity of the field solution turns out to be written formally as the *minimal substitution* and the *parallel transport* of ordinary electrodynamics, respectively.

A. Minimal substitution

We now want to apply the geometrodynamical description of interaction (12) to the following local infinitesimal transformation of variables

$$x^\mu(x) \rightarrow x'^\mu \sim x^\mu - e x^a \Omega_a^\mu(x). \quad (22)$$

The coefficient of the expansion is denoted by e and address as *gauge coupling*. In this paper we will work in the approximation in which this transformation is a local isometries, *i.e.* we limit our study to the case in which the Jacobian is $\sqrt{-g'} \simeq 1$.

In terms of the formalism of (16), a local isometry is described by

$$\Lambda_\mu^a(x) \simeq \delta_\mu^a - e \Omega_\mu^a(x) \quad (23)$$

whereas the tangent transformation [15] is described by the local tetrad

$$e_\mu^a(x) \simeq \delta_\mu^a - e \omega_\mu^a(x). \quad (24)$$

As we will discuss in sec.(IV D), these isometries can be regarded as belonging to some local subgroups of the Lorentz transformations. Moreover the requirement of local isometries implies that $\omega_\mu^a(x)$ is antisymmetric (Killing equations). For the sake of simplicity we assume that such an isometry is a unitary transformation

$$\omega_\mu^a(x) \in U(1).$$

According to (18) the finite and tangent transformations are related by

$$x^a \Omega_a^\mu(x) = \int^{x^a} dx^a \omega_a^\mu(x). \quad (25)$$

To each point $x = X$ of the inertial frame S we are associating a local Lorentz reference frame S' , as represented by the orthogonal tetrad $e_\mu^a(X)$. As already noticed, the tetrad $e_\mu^a(x)$ encodes the information, point by point, of a corresponding interaction scheme. In this case the information is contained in $\omega_a^\mu(x)$ which in turn can be used to define a vectorial field $\bar{A}_\mu(x)$ as

$$\bar{A}_\mu(x) \equiv \omega_\mu^a(x) \bar{p}_a. \quad (26)$$

Thus the vectorial fields $\bar{A}_\mu(x)$ can be used to encode the particular interaction scheme (22). In particular, the variation of four-momentum (12) associated with this local isometry is in this case given by

$$\bar{p}'_\mu(x) \sim \bar{p}_\mu - e \bar{A}_\mu(x) \quad (27)$$

which formally is the *minimal substitution* of the vectorial field $\bar{A}_\mu(x)$.

Since we are assuming that the local isometry (22) is a unitary transformation $\omega(x) \in U(1)$, we say that the vectorial field $A_\mu(x)$ is an *abelian* field. In sec.(IV D) we will discuss the geometrical meaning of this assumption as well as the generalization to *non-abelian* isometries.

Under such a local isometric change of flat manifold $g_{\mu\nu}(x) \simeq \eta_{\mu\nu}$, the resulting transformed action (21) has the same structure of the original one, *i.e.* the equations of motion remain unchanged. Nevertheless the boundary of the transformed action turns out to be locally rotated with respect to the original action (11). In fact, the resulting action is

$$\bar{S} = \frac{1}{2} \int^{T'^\mu(X)} d^4x [\partial'_\mu \bar{\Phi}'^\dagger(x) \partial'^\mu \bar{\Phi}'(x) - \bar{M}^2 \bar{\Phi}'^\dagger(x) \bar{\Phi}'(x)]. \quad (28)$$

This action has indeed transformed boundary at $T'^\mu(X)$ with respect to the persistent boundary at T^μ of the original action, according to (20). Therefore its fundamental solution $\bar{\Phi}'(x)$ in the point $x = X$ turns out to be different from the original fundamental solution $\bar{\Phi}(x)$. The transformed solution $\bar{\Phi}'(x)$ has periodicity $\tau'^\mu(X)$ varying from point to point in order to describe interaction. The free solution $\bar{\Phi}(x)$ has the persistent periodicity $\tau^\mu = T^\mu$ of an isolated particle.

1. Global Isometry

To formulate interactions in terms of gauge fields we need to express the rotations of the boundary in terms of *internal transformations* of the field.

Here we consider the particularly simple case of a *global* isometry

$$\Lambda_\mu^\alpha(x) = e_\mu^\alpha(x) \equiv e_\mu^\alpha, \quad (29)$$

For reasons that will be clear later we address this case as *pure gauge* — this terminology is not completely equivalent to ordinary QFT.

In this case the tetrad is homogeneous, it does not depend on x . The resulting four-periodicity $\tau'^\mu = e_a^\mu T^a$ and four-momentum $\bar{p}'_\mu = e_\mu^a \bar{p}_a$ of the transformed field $\bar{\Phi}'$ varies globally. The transformed four-periodicity (5) coincides with the compactification four-vector of the transformed action $\tau'^\mu = T'^\mu$.

In every interaction point $x = X$ the fundamental solution $\bar{\Phi}'(x')$ associated with the transformed action (28) is related to the original solution $\bar{\Phi}(x)$ by the following transformation

$$\bar{\Phi}(x) = \bar{N} e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar} x^\mu \bar{p}_\mu} \rightarrow \bar{\Phi}'(x') = \bar{N} e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar} x'^\mu \bar{p}'_\mu} \quad (30)$$

It is easy to see that, as long as $\bar{\Phi}(x)$ is a fundamental solution of the free action, under this transformation $\bar{\Phi}'(x')$ is automatically the correct fundamental solution of the transformed action (28). In fact, it has transformed four-periodicity $T'^\mu = e_a^\mu T^a$, according to the de Broglie phase harmony.

Now we expand the global transformation e_μ^α as in (22), so that the interaction scheme is formally the *minimal substitution* (27); \bar{A}_μ and \bar{p}'_μ are homogeneous (constant). The physical effect of this *pure gauge* is a global transformation of reference frame. Thus, under this global isometry the field transforms as

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\Phi}(x) = \bar{N} e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar} x_\mu \bar{p}^\mu} &\rightarrow \bar{\Phi}'(x') = \bar{N} e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar} x'_\mu (\bar{p}^\mu - e \bar{A}^\mu)} \\ &= \bar{V}(x') \bar{\Phi}(x'). \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

This also means that to our transformation of variables there is associated an *internal transformation* of the field described by

$$\bar{V}(x) = e^{\frac{ie}{\hbar} x_\mu \bar{A}^\mu}. \quad (32)$$

We call \bar{A}_μ *gauge connection* and $\bar{V}(x)$ *parallel-transport*. Since we are assuming abelian transformation of variables, the resulting *internal transformation* of the fundamental solution (31) generates an abelian *parallel-transport* $\bar{V}(x) \in U(1)$.

We also introduce the *covariant derivative* of the transformed field $\bar{\Phi}'$ as

$$\partial_\mu \bar{\Phi}(x) = \partial_\mu [\bar{V}^{-1}(x) \bar{\Phi}'(x)] = D_\mu \bar{\Phi}'(x). \quad (33)$$

Thus the covariant derivative associated with a global isometry is

$$\partial_\mu \rightarrow D_\mu = \partial_\mu - \frac{ie}{\hbar} \bar{A}_\mu \quad (34)$$

It is important to note that, even though the transformed fundamental solution $\bar{\Phi}'(x)$ has a transformed four-periodicity T'^μ , the terms $D_\mu \bar{\Phi}'(x)$ and $\bar{V}^{-1}(x) \bar{\Phi}'(x)$ have the same persistent four-periodicity T^μ as $\partial_\mu \bar{\Phi}(x)$ and the original fundamental mode $\bar{\Phi}(x)$. We will address this important aspect by saying that the *covariant derivative* and the inverse of the *parallel transport* tunes the periodicity T'^μ of the transformed fundamental mode $\bar{\Phi}'(x)$ to the periodicity T^μ of the free fundamental mode $\bar{\Phi}(x)$. We will next generalize these considerations to local isometries.

B. Local Isometry

In the general case of local isometry, the tetrad $e_\mu^\alpha(x)$ varies from point to point. Thus we must take into account that, at every point $x = X$, the transformed fundamental mode $\bar{\Phi}'(x)$ must have local four-periodicity $\tau'^\mu(x)|_{x=X}$ in order to be a solution of the transformed action (28) with boundary at $T'^\mu(x)|_{x=X}$ given by (20). This also means that the transformed fundamental solution $\bar{\Phi}'(x)$ must have four-momentum $\bar{p}'_\mu(x)|_{x=X}$ in order to satisfy (13) in $x = X$. In the approximation $e_\mu^\alpha(x) \sim e_\mu^\alpha(x')$ and considering that the normalization factor \bar{N} is invariant under isometries, the fundamental mode $\bar{\Phi}'(x')$ solution of the transformed action (28) can be written, according to our notation (18), as

$$\bar{\Phi}(x) = \bar{N} e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar} x \cdot \bar{p}} \rightarrow \bar{\Phi}'(x') = \bar{N} e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar} \int^{x'} dx^\mu \bar{p}'_\mu(x)}. \quad (35)$$

To check this, besides the de Broglie phase harmony, the analogy with the CKM formalism and the analogy with the formalism of frequency modulated signals, we may note that the derivative operator $i\hbar \partial_\mu$ actually gives the correct transformed four-momentum $\bar{p}'_\mu(x)$ in the new reference frame

$$i\hbar \partial_\mu \bar{\Phi}(x) = \bar{p}_\mu \bar{\Phi}(x) \rightarrow i\hbar \partial_\mu \bar{\Phi}'(x') = \bar{p}'_\mu(x') \bar{\Phi}'(x') \quad (36)$$

According to the definition of the local tetrad $e_\mu^\alpha(x)$ in (24), the fundamental solution $\bar{\Phi}'(x')$ of (28) is obtained from the free fundamental solution $\bar{\Phi}(x)$ by the following *internal transformation* of the field

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\Phi}(x) = \bar{N} e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar} x \cdot \bar{p}} &\rightarrow \bar{\Phi}'(x') = \bar{N} e^{\frac{ie}{\hbar} \int^{x'} dx \cdot \bar{A}(x)} e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar} x' \cdot \bar{p}} \\ &= \bar{V}(x') \bar{\Phi}(x'). \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

Hence the *parallel-transport* $\bar{V}(x)$ describing the *internal transformation* of fundamental solution under this local abelian transformation of variables is formally a Wilson line of the gauge connection

$$\bar{V}(x) = e^{\frac{ie}{\hbar} \int^x dx \cdot \bar{A}(x)}. \quad (38)$$

This allows one to pass from a fundamental solution with persistent periodicity τ^μ to a fundamental solution with transformed local periodicity $\tau'^\mu(x)$. In this way, as long as $\bar{\Phi}(x)$ is solution of the free action, $\bar{\Phi}'(x')$ is automatically solution of the transformed action (28). The

FIG. 1. Diagrammatic description of the local isometry $\Lambda(x)$ transforming a free fundamental field $\bar{\Phi}(X)$ of persistent four-momentum \bar{p}_μ , four-periodicity τ^μ and compactification four-length $T^\mu = \tau^\mu$, from the inertial frame S to the reference frame S' . The resulting fundamental field solution $\bar{\Phi}'(X)$ has locally transformed four-momentum $\bar{p}'_\mu(X)$, four-periodicity $\tau'^\mu(X)$ and compactification four-length $T'^\mu(X) \neq T^\mu$. The conservation of stress-energy-momentum tensor involves the Noether current $\bar{J}_\mu(X)$.

vectorial field $\bar{A}_\mu(x)$ describes the modulations of the four-periodicity of “periodic phenomenon” under the local transformations of variables.

The generalization to local isometry of the *covariant derivative* (33) of the transformed field $\bar{\Phi}'(x)$ is

$$\partial_\mu \rightarrow D_\mu = \partial_\mu - \frac{ie}{\hbar} \bar{A}_\mu(x) \quad (39)$$

Also in this more general case we find that the *covariant derivative*, as well as the inverse of the *parallel-transport*, *tunes* the locally varying periodicity $\tau'^\mu(x)$ of the transformed fundamental mode $\bar{\Phi}'$ to the persistent periodicity $\tau^\mu = T^\mu$ of the free fundamental mode $\bar{\Phi}$. This *tuning* through *parallel transport* will be used to allow a field with locally varying four-periodicity $\tau'^\mu(x)$ to fulfill the variational principle in an action with persistent boundary $\tau^\mu = T^\mu$.

C. Noether Currents

The formalism of field theory in compact 4D allows one to relate, through the variational principle, transformation of variables δx and *internal transformations* of the field $\delta\bar{\Phi}(x)$. This can be easily seen from the role of the *parallel-transport* (38). The *internal transformation* associated to the local abelian isometry (22) is indeed

$$\delta\bar{\Phi}(x) = \bar{\Phi}'(x) - \bar{\Phi}(x) = ie\bar{A}_\nu(x)\bar{\Phi}(x)\delta x^\nu. \quad (40)$$

To understand the role of these *internal transformations* of the field we consider the role of the boundary terms in the variation of the action. In the approximation of local isometries, the original and transformed action differ by an explicit variation of the boundary

$$\delta\bar{S} = \int^{T'^\mu} d^4x' \bar{\mathcal{L}}'(\bar{\Phi}'^i, x') - \int^{T^\mu} d^4x \bar{\mathcal{L}}(\bar{\Phi}^i, x) \quad (41)$$

As represented diagrammatically in fig.(1), the stress-energy-momentum of the fundamental mode $\bar{\Phi}$ is not conserved because of the local transformation of reference frame. In fact, it is easy to see from (41) that the conservation of the stress-energy-momentum tensor involves the contribution of the *internal transformation* of the field (40); that is, of the current

$$\bar{J}_\mu = ie[\bar{\Phi}^* D_\mu \bar{\Phi} - D_\mu \bar{\Phi}^* \bar{\Phi}]. \quad (42)$$

The interesting aspect of this analysis is that actually the current \bar{J}_μ has the same form as the Noether current of an abelian gauge invariant theory with *internal transformation* (40), as long as we identify the connection $\bar{A}_\mu(x)$ with an abelian gauge field.

IV. GAUGE INTERACTION

The formalism introduced so far is very useful to describe the geometrodynamics associated with a given interaction scheme of an elementary particle. However it does not explicitly take into account the conservation of four-momentum. This is because it involves a transformation of reference frame. As we have pointed out in the Noether analysis, this is related to the local variations of the boundary. From a computational point of view it would be easier to describe the same interaction scheme in terms of an action whose boundary is invariant under isometric transformation of variables. In this way the currents related to the transformation of the boundary will be directly expressed in terms of symmetries of the Lagrangian. The possibility of such a formalism is offered by the fact that the periodicities of the fields can be *tuned* through *parallel transport*. The result will be an ordinary gauge invariant theory.

A. Tuned action

We want to define a new formalism to describe $\bar{\Phi}'(x)$ under the interaction scheme (27) such that there is an explicit conservation of four-momentum. Our strategy will be to write a new action, which we will call *tuned action*, containing the same physical information of the transformed action (28) but with persistent boundary at T^μ . Similarly to the transformed action, this *tuned* can be obtained directly from the free action (11).

To build the *tuned* action we need to know that to a change in the periodicity of the fundamental field solution there is an associated *internal transformation* (37), *i.e.* a *parallel-transport*. If we want to vary the four-periodicity of a field in an action with given boundary, and at the same time fulfill the variational principle, we must use the *parallel-transport* to *tune* the four-periodicity of the field. Since the only terms involved in the BCs are the derivative terms (through integration by parts), the *tuned* action can be obtained from the free action by modifying

FIG. 2. Diagrammatic description of the local isometry $\Lambda(x)$ in terms of the *tuning* mediated by the vectorial field $A_\mu(X)$ with local four-momentum $\bar{p}_\mu^\gamma(X)$ and four-periodicity $\tau_\mu^\gamma(X)$. The conservation of four-momentum is manifest from the fact that the free fundamental field $\bar{\Phi}(X)$ and the interacting system $\bar{\Phi}'(X)$ and $A_\mu(X)$ have the same compactification length T^μ .

only derivative terms. We have already noticed, for instance, that the corresponding covariant derivative (39) allows one to *tune* the periodicity of $\bar{\Phi}'(x)$ to the periodicity of $\bar{\Phi}(x)$.

In this case the interaction can be described in terms of symmetries of the Lagrangian rather than in terms of the variations of the boundary. Hence the interacting field $\bar{\Phi}'(x)$ will be described by different equations of motion and the currents (42) will be the conserved currents associated with the symmetries of the Lagrangian.

At a mathematical level this can be easily achieved through the *parallel-transport* $\bar{V}(x)$, by explicitly writing in the free action (11) the fundamental solution $\bar{\Phi}(x)$ as a function of the transformed fundamental solution $\bar{\Phi}'(x)$, *i.e.* by using (37). In this way we find

$$\begin{aligned} \int^{T^\mu} d^4x \bar{\mathcal{L}}(\partial_\mu \bar{\Phi}, \bar{\Phi}) &\rightarrow \int^{T^\mu} d^4x \bar{\mathcal{L}}(\partial_\mu \bar{V}^{-1} \bar{\Phi}', \bar{V}^{-1} \bar{\Phi}') \\ &= \int^{T^\mu} d^4x \bar{\mathcal{L}}(D_\mu \bar{\Phi}', \bar{\Phi}') \end{aligned} \quad (43)$$

According to the definition (39), the derivative terms $\partial_\mu \bar{\Phi}(x)$ of the original action must be replaced by the covariant derivative $D_\mu \bar{\Phi}'(x)$ in order to *tune* locally the periodicity $\tau'^\mu(x)$ to T^μ . We have also used the fact that non-derivative terms, such as the mass term, contributes only to the equations of motion, but not to the BCs (the periodicity of the solution in such terms can be arbitrarily varied without compromising the variational principle).

Therefore the tuned Lagrangian can be directly obtained from the free Lagrangian by replacing the ordinary derivatives with covariant derivatives

$$\bar{\mathcal{L}}_{\text{tuned}}(\partial_\mu \bar{\Phi}', \bar{\Phi}', \bar{A}_\mu) = \bar{\mathcal{L}}(D_\mu \bar{\Phi}', \bar{\Phi}'). \quad (44)$$

In the specific interaction scheme (27) for the fundamental scalar mode of a cyclic field with mass \bar{M} , the *tuned* action is

$$\bar{S} = \frac{1}{2} \int^{T^\mu} d^4x [D_\mu \bar{\Phi}'^*(x) D^\mu \bar{\Phi}'(x) - \bar{M}^2 \bar{\Phi}'^\dagger(x) \bar{\Phi}'(x)] \quad (45)$$

The tuned action is related to the original free action by *parallel-transport*. If $\bar{\Phi}(x)$ is the fundamental solution of the original free action, then the transformed fundamental solution $\bar{\Phi}'(x)$ automatically minimizes (45). On the other hand $\bar{\Phi}'(x')$ is also the solution of the transformed action (28). Hence the tuned action (45) contains the same physical information of the transformed action (28).

The vectorial field $\bar{A}_\mu(x)$ encodes the variation of periodicity of an interacting system giving rise to covariant derivatives in the tuned action. If we identify the *gauge connection* $\bar{A}_\mu(x)$ with an ordinary gauge field, the tune action (45) is formally a gauged KG action with boundary.

In this way we have given a geometrical meaning to covariant derivatives, parallel-transport, and gauge connections, in terms of variations of periodicities. This picture can be intuitively interpreted by imagining the transporting of the arms of a clock with given periodicity on a closed path in a curved manifold. At the end of the loop we must either *retune* the arms of the clock through *parallel-transport* or to assume that the clock has a different periodicity. Indeed the *parallel-transport* allows one “to describe the variation of periodicity associated with deformation of the underlying manifold in a background independent way”, [19].

B. Gauge Invariance

At a mathematical level the *parallel-transport* $\bar{V}(x)$ allows one the possibility to *tune* periodicity of terms of the Lagrangian to the periodicity imposed by the boundary of the action. However it is easy to note that such a parallel-transport, as well as the gauge connection, is not uniquely defined: the tuned action (45) has acquired a further invariance which we call — for obvious reasons — *gauge invariance*.

It is well known that (45) is invariant under the following transformation

$$\bar{A}_\mu(x) \rightarrow \bar{A}'_\mu(x) = \bar{A}_\mu(x) - e \partial_\mu \bar{\theta}(x), \quad (46)$$

In the *parallel-transport* $\bar{V}(x)$, which is formally a Wilson line (38), this transformation generates boundary terms which can be absorbed by the following phase transformation of the fundamental scalar mode

$$\bar{\Phi}'(x') \rightarrow \bar{\Phi}''(x) = \bar{N} e^{-\frac{e}{\hbar} e \bar{\theta}(x)} \bar{\Phi}'(x) \quad (47)$$

The resulting local phase transformation of the field is

$$\bar{U}(x) = e^{-\frac{e}{\hbar} e \bar{\theta}(x)}. \quad (48)$$

This phase turns out to be of the same kind as the *parallel-transport* $\bar{V}(x)$ or of the local isometry which generates it. Therefore $\bar{U}(x) \in U(1)$ in the case of abelian isometry. We have finally shown that a fundamental mode subject to a local abelian isometry is described by an abelian gauge invariant action.

The gauge invariance $U(1)$ is now a symmetry of the tuned Lagrangian. Therefore the gauge transformations do not affect the boundary of the action. In other words we have found that gauge invariance identifies particular class of isometries describing the same interaction scheme. For this reason we call them *gauge orbits* (we only mention that such a gauge orbit can be regarded as an *holonomy*, since it corresponds to an isometry whose parameter $\omega(x)$ is a total derivative and “the boundary of a boundary is zero”).

To meaning of the *tuning* of the field described so far can be generalized. Gauge invariant terms allows one to tune the periodicity of the fundamental field solution to the periodicity imposed, through the variational principle, by the boundary of the action. This is essentially because the *parallel-transport* $\bar{V}(x)$ tunes the periodicity of the bosonic field solutions.

At this point we can repeat the variational analysis of par.(III C). Noether’s theorem can be applied directly to the tuned Lagrangian instead of the transformed action. Since the tuning formalism allows a description in which the boundary of the action does not vary under isometric transformation of variables, it is easy to show that the Noether currents (42) are directly associated with the symmetries of the tuned Lagrangian. In this case the Noether analysis is completely parallel to the one of ordinary gauge theory.

The remaining step to prove that the interaction scheme associated with such a local abelian isometry is nothing but usual gauge interaction, is to find that the dynamics of the abelian gauge field $A_\mu(x)$ is actually described by the Maxwell equation.

C. Yang-Mills action

The tuned action (45) is formally a $U(1)$ gauge invariant action. The tuning of the interacting field has been obtained at the expense of the introduction of a new field in the theory. This is the gauge connection $\bar{A}_\mu(x)$. It compensates the variation of four-periodicity of the interacting field in order to have a *tuning* to the persistent boundary of the action. Therefore it is natural to interpret $\bar{A}_\mu(x)$ as a new dynamical field with given four-momentum, in general different from \bar{p}_μ or $\bar{p}'_\mu(x)$, and thus with given four-periodicity, in general different from T^μ or $T'^\mu(x)$. This is illustrated in fig.(2). This requires one to introduce a kinetic term for $\bar{A}_\mu(x)$. Similarly to the interacting fundamental field solution $\bar{\Phi}'(x)$ of the tuned action (45), this kinetic term may appear in an action with persistent integration region T^μ , in order to describe explicitly the conservation of four-momentum. That is, we want to add a kinetic term for $\bar{A}_\mu(x)$ to the tuned action (45) — a similar analysis can be done for the transformed action.

From the correspondence between gauge invariance and the periodicity tuning, we require that such a kinetic term must be gauge invariant. In fact, only in this

way can the periodicity of $\bar{A}_\mu(x)$ be tuned with the BCs imposed by the tuned action. In particular we have already noticed that such a tuning of the periodicity of the field in derivative terms, such as in the kinetic terms, is possible by using covariant derivatives. Through suitable covariant derivatives the four-periodicity of $\bar{A}_\mu(x)$ can be tuned to T^μ .

Therefore, by following the same requirement of gauge invariance as in ordinary field theory, we infer that the correct kinetic terms allowed for $\bar{A}_\mu(x)$ by the variational principle is the gauge invariant term $-\frac{1}{4}\bar{F}_{\mu\nu}\bar{F}^{\mu\nu}$, where $\bar{F}^{\mu\nu}$ is the field strength. In fact, it is well known that the derivatives in the field strength can be replaced by arbitrary covariant derivatives of the gauge field itself $\bar{F}^{\mu\nu}(x) = D'_\mu\bar{A}_\nu(x) - D'_\nu\bar{A}_\mu(x)$. This means that in such a kinetic term the periodicity of the gauge field is tuned to the characteristic periodicity of the action through an appropriate covariant derivative (in general different from the one of the matter field [24]).

Finally the full action describing the interaction scheme (22) consistently with the variational principle is

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{S}_{YM} = \int^{T^\mu} d^4x \left\{ -\frac{1}{4}\bar{F}_{\mu\nu}(x)\bar{F}^{\mu\nu}(x) \right. \\ \left. + \frac{1}{2} [D_\mu\bar{\Phi}'^*(x)D^\mu\bar{\Phi}'(x) - \bar{M}^2\bar{\Phi}'^*(x)\bar{\Phi}'(x)] \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (49)$$

This action is nothing but the usual non-quantum (tree-level) abelian Yang-Mills action (in a finite volume) describing a matter field solution with four-momentum $\bar{p}'_\mu(x)$ interacting with a gauge field $\bar{A}_\mu(x)$ and total four-momentum \bar{p}_μ .

It must be noticed that the simultaneous minimization of the above action at the boundary for both the fields $\bar{\Phi}'(x)$ and $\bar{A}_\mu(x)$, or equivalently the requirement of gauge invariance of the action, constrains the general form of the gauge field. In turn the so far generic form of the abelian transformation of variables (24) is constrained to a particular subclass, modulo gauge orbits. In fact the fundamental field solution \bar{A}_μ is no more a generic vectorial field. That is, according to the variational principle, it must be solution of the equations of motion associated with (49), *i.e.* it has Maxwell dynamics. For instance this means that $\bar{A}_\mu(x)$ is massless and has only two transversal *d.o.f.* On the other hand, through (26), the Maxwell dynamics of gauge field $\bar{A}_\mu(x)$ corresponds to related dynamics of the coefficients $\omega_\mu^\alpha(x)$ of the transformation of variables. Only isometries (24) satisfying this dynamics and which we will address as *transversally polarized* are allowed by the variational principle. The result is a geometrodynamical description of ordinary gauge interactions.

The kinetic term of the gauge field has been introduced because the variational principle requires gauge invariant terms. This requirement of gauge invariance is actually the usual way to introduce such a kinetic term in ordinary non-quantum YM theory. The same argument can be used to introduce the kinematic terms for the gauge

field in the formalism of the transformed action (28). In this case we must assume covariant derivatives only in the field strength such that the periodicity of the gauge field is tuned to the locally varying periodicity T^μ of the interacting field.

“The modern viewpoint”, [3, 25], to introduce gauge interaction in ordinary field theory is to impose a *parallel-transport* (38) — sometimes called *connection*— to a matter field. In this way the derivative terms generate covariant derivatives and the Lagrangian is gauge invariant. Thus, in ordinary field theory, “*the covariant derivative and the transformation law of the connection \bar{A}_μ follow from the postulate of local phase rotation symmetry*” [25]. From the viewpoint of field theory in compact 4D the same gauge invariant Lagrangian is obtained from the geometrodynamics allowed by the variational principle, without postulating it. In fact we have seen that the *parallel-transport* of a matter field arises naturally to tune variations of periodicity associated with local transformations of variables with the periodicity imposed by the minimization of the action at the boundary. The invariance of the action under transformation of variables induces an *internal transformation* of the field solutions. This reveals an intuitive geometrical nature of gauge interactions. This important and non-trivial result is in the spirit of Weyl’s original proposal of a geometrical interpretation of gauge interactions.

The formalism of compact 4D makes manifest this geometrodynamical interpretation of gauge interaction, because it explicitly relates *internal transformations* of the field solution to variations of the BCs. The same arguments can be in principle repeated in ordinary field theory by replacing the compact integration region T^μ with Σ^μ and the PBCs with SBCs.

D. Non-abelian case

We conclude this section by giving a generalization to *non-abelian* local transformations of variables and a possible geometrical meaning of our interaction scheme.

To generalize our result to the non-abelian case we must assume that the transformation of variables (23) originating our interaction scheme (27) is an element of a non-abelian group H . This implies that in the equation obtained so far we must perform the following substitution from an abelian vectorial field to a non-abelian

$$\bar{A}_\mu(x) \rightarrow \bar{A}_\mu^i(x)\tau^i$$

where τ^i are generators of H . As a consequence of the commutation relations of the generators the *parallel-transport* must be written as an path-ordered Wilson line

$$\bar{V}(x') = e^{\frac{ie}{\hbar} \int^{x'} dx \cdot \bar{A}(x)} \rightarrow \bar{V}(x') = P[e^{\frac{ie}{\hbar} \int^{x'} dx \cdot \bar{A}^a(x)\tau^a}]. \quad (50)$$

A similar redefinition must be considered for the covariant derivatives. In this way (49) turns out to describe a Yang-Mills theory with gauge invariance H .

We have described gauge interaction in the approximation where the transformation of variables (22) is a local isometry. In this approximation the lengths of the four vector are preserved and we do not consider variations of the normalizations of the fields [26].

Moreover the variational principle allows only a particular subclass of *polarized* local isometries, modulo *gauge orbits*. In this way the dynamics for the related vectorial field turns out to be the usual Maxwell’s dynamics.

We can now associate the *polarized* isometries (23) describing our interaction scheme to corresponding *polarized* local Lorentz transformations. By representing the Lorentz group as $SU_L(2) \otimes SU_R(2)$, the most general global isometry which we may consider is $\omega \in SU_L(2) \otimes SU_R(2)$. In this case $e\omega_\mu^a = gw_\mu^{ai}\tau^i + g'y_\mu^{ai}\tau^i$ where w_μ^{ai} and y_μ^{ai} , g and g' are the coefficients and the coupling of $SU_L(2)$ and $SU_R(2)$, respectively. The index $i = 1, 2, 3$ is associated with the generators τ^i of $SU(2)$. The global components of this isometry describe *pure-gauge* transformations (global Lorentz transformations) whereas the local polarized components correspond to the gauging of the corresponding subgroup $H \subset SU_L(2) \otimes SU_R(2)$. For instance the abelian gauge theory describing ordinary classical electrodynamics can be obtained by assuming that only the corresponding polarized and abelian Lorentz transformations with generator in $U_{em}(1) \subset SU_L(2) \otimes SU_R(2)$ are local.

Similarly we can imagine to describe electroweak interactions by assuming that the local polarized isometries are only those associated with the Lorentz subgroups $SU_L(2) \otimes U_Y(1) \subset SU_L(2) \otimes SU_R(2)$ (the gauging the electroweak group from a larger global group $SU_L(2) \otimes SU_R(2)$ is typical in technicolor models and useful to describe the custodial symmetry, see for instance [27]). As for the abelian case (26) we can define gauge fields associated with $SU_L(2)$ and $U_Y(1)$ as $W_\mu(x) = W_\mu^i(x)\tau^i = w_\mu^{ai}(x)\tau^i\bar{p}_a$ and $Y_\mu(x) = Y_\mu^3(x)\tau^3 = y_\mu^{a3}(x)\tau^3\bar{p}_a$. Indeed we have the remarkable possibility to relate the electroweak gauge group to a local Lorentz subgroup.

A possible generalization of this geometrodynamical description of gauge interaction to fermionic fields has a natural realization on the *Zitterbewegung* models. Originally proposed by Schrödinger this idea provides a semiclassical interpretation of the spin and of the magnetic momentum in terms of a cyclic dynamics whose periodicity is actually the de Broglie periodicities of the fermions, see for instance [28]. Such a trembling motion of the fermions can be derived from the Dirac equation.

Finally, it is interesting to mention that the geometrodynamical description of gauge interaction described so far has a deep motivation in the so called Kaluza’s miracle [4]. This can be seen by considering the dualism of the theory to an XD theory [1, 16]. Under this dualism, the metric (15) associated to the substitution of variable (22) turns out to be a Kaluza-like XD metric.

V. QUANTUM BEHAVIOR

So far we have limited our study to the fundamental mode $\bar{\Phi}(x)$ of the cyclic field $\Phi(x)$. This corresponds to study the theory at tree-level. In fact the fundamental mode can be matched with a corresponding single mode of a non-quantized KG field with corresponding four-frequency. Because of this matching with a KG mode, the fundamental mode can be in principle quantized in the usual way by imposing explicitly commutation relations and obtaining ordinary QED. However, as shown in [1] and summarized in this section, the classical evolution of a cyclic field (with all its energy excitations) has remarkable correspondences with the quantum evolution of ordinary second quantized fields. This correspondence has been checked explicitly in both the canonical formulation of QM (the theory has implicit commutation relations) and the Feynman Path Integral (FPI) formulation, as well as for many other peculiar quantum phenomena and problems (including Schrodinger problems [1, 6, 29]). The correspondence with the FPI formulated for free systems in [1], will be generalized to the interacting system studied so far. In fact, the evolution of an interacting cyclic also is Markovian evolutions and an Hilbert space can be defined locally. The assumption of PBCs can be regarded as a semi-classical quantization condition for relativistic fields.

A. Mode expansion

To investigate the quantum behavior of the theory we need to use the most generic cyclic field solutions of the action in compact 4D. By considering the discrete Fourier transform associated with the cyclic 4D of the theory, it is easy to figure out that such a periodic field has a quantized energy-momentum spectrum. For the sake of simplicity with topology \mathbb{S}^1 so that the spectrum is described by the single quantum number n .

From the relation $\bar{E}(\bar{\mathbf{p}}) = \hbar\bar{\omega}(\bar{\mathbf{p}})$, the intrinsic time periodicity $T_t(\bar{\mathbf{p}})$ of cyclic field in a given reference frame denoted by $\bar{\mathbf{p}}$ implies a quantized energy spectrum $E_n(\bar{\mathbf{p}}) = \hbar\omega_n(\bar{\mathbf{p}})$. In free case the PBCs yields to $\omega_n(\bar{\mathbf{p}}) = n\bar{\omega}(\bar{\mathbf{p}})$, which is nothing but the harmonic frequency spectrum of a vibrating string with the characteristic time periodicity of the field [30]. Thus this formulation can be regarded as the field theory analogous to the semi-classical quantization of a ‘‘particle’’ in a box. It also shares deep analogies with the Matsubara and the Kaluza-Klein (KK) theories [16, 31]. Indeed, from this harmonic spectrum and from (9) we see that free cyclic fields reproduce the same quantized energy spectrum of ordinary second quantized fields (after normal ordering)

$$\bar{E}_n(\bar{\mathbf{p}}) = n\sqrt{\bar{\mathbf{p}}^2c^2 + \bar{M}^2c^4}. \quad (51)$$

A free cyclic field $\Phi(\mathbf{x}, t)$ (here $x^\mu = \{ct, \mathbf{x}\}$) with intrinsic periodicity $T_t(\bar{\mathbf{p}})$, solution of the action in compact 4D

(4), is a tower of energy eigenmodes $\phi_n(x)$ with eigenvalues (51). Furthermore, the time periodicity induces a periodicity λ_x to the modulo of the spatial dimensions according to (7). Hence, similarly to the quantization of the energy momentum, there is a quantization of the modulo of the spatial momentum $|\mathbf{p}_n| = n|\mathbf{p}| = nh/\lambda_x$. The fact that T^μ is a four-vector means there is a single periodicity induced between the time dimension and the modulo of the spatial dimension. The topology of the theory is \mathbb{S}^1 . This implies that the resulting quantization is to be expressed in terms of the single quantum number n . It is important to note, however, that together with this single fundamental periodicity \mathbb{S}^1 , in spherical problems (such as the Hydrogen atom, the 3D harmonic oscillator, or problems with particular bounded geometries), two other cyclic variables (or their deformations) must be considered: the spherical angles $\theta \in [0, 2\pi]$ and $\psi \in [0, \pi]$. As well-known from ordinary QM they lead to the ordinary quantization of angular momentum. In this case the cyclic field would be written as a sum over two additional quantum numbers, typically denoted by (m, l) , and the topology of the fields would be $\mathbb{S}^{(1,2)}$ (PBCs for the transverse mode of a field, as in the front-light-quantization, can be used to calculate important predictions of perturbative QED as shown in [21]). For simplicity we will not consider the expansion in spherical harmonics (or their deformations). We will investigate only the quantization of the four-momentum spectrum associated with \mathbb{S}^1 . In the free case is an harmonic one

$$p_{n\mu} = n\bar{p}_\mu. \quad (52)$$

Depending whether we want to make explicit the normalization factor of the energy eigenmodes, we write the cyclic field solution by using the following notations,

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi(x) &= \sum_n \Phi_n(x) = \sum_n \mathcal{N}_n \alpha_n(\bar{\mathbf{p}}) \phi_n(x) = \\ &= \sum_n \mathcal{N}_n \alpha_n(\bar{\mathbf{p}}) e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar} p_n \cdot x}. \end{aligned} \quad (53)$$

As already mentioned we assume that the normalization factor \mathcal{N}_n is invariant under isometries. The coefficients of the Fourier expansion are represented by $\alpha_n(\bar{\mathbf{p}})$. The non-quantum limit corresponds to the case where the cyclic field solutions can be approximated with the fundamental mode $\Phi(x) \sim \bar{\Phi}(x) = \bar{\mathcal{N}}\bar{\phi}(x)$, *i.e.* when only the fundamental level is largely excited: $\bar{\alpha}(\bar{\mathbf{p}}) \sim 1$ and $\alpha_{n \neq 1}(\bar{\mathbf{p}}) \sim 0$.

B. Correspondence with Quantum Mechanics

Next we summarize the correspondence of field theory in compact 4D with QFT ms [1, 6]. We note that the evolution of the free cyclic field (53) along the compact time dimension is described by the so-called ‘‘bulk’’ equations of motion $(\partial_t^2 + \omega_n^2)\phi_n(x, t) = 0$ — for the sake of

simplicity in this section we assume a single spatial dimension x . Thus the time evolution of the energy eigenmodes $\phi_n(x, t)$ can be written as first order differential equations

$$i\hbar\partial_t\phi_n(x, t) = E_n\phi_n(x, t). \quad (54)$$

The cyclic field (53) is a sum of eigenmodes of an harmonic system. Actually this classical harmonic system is the typical system which can be described in a Hilbert space. In fact, the energy eigenmodes of a cyclic field form a complete set with respect to the inner product

$$\langle\phi_{n'}(t')|\phi_n(t)\rangle \equiv \int^{\lambda_x} \frac{dx}{\lambda_x} \phi_{n'}^*(x, t')\phi_n(x, t). \quad (55)$$

They energy eigenmodes can also be used to define Hilbert eigenstates

$$\langle x, t|\phi_n\rangle \equiv \frac{\phi_n(x, t)}{\sqrt{\lambda_x}}. \quad (56)$$

As obvious in the non-interacting case where the cyclic fields have persistent periodicity, the integration region λ_x can be extended to an arbitrary large integer number of periods $V_x = N'\lambda_x$. That is, by assuming $N' \rightarrow \infty$, it can be extended to an infinite region.

In this Hilbert space we can formally build an Hamiltonian operator defined as

$$\mathcal{H}|\phi_n\rangle \equiv \hbar\omega_n|\phi_n\rangle. \quad (57)$$

Similar considerations hold for the spatial dimension and the momentum operator is defined as

$$\mathcal{P}|\phi_n\rangle \equiv -\hbar k_n|\phi_n\rangle, \quad (58)$$

where $k_n = n\bar{k} = nh/\lambda_x$. A Hilbert state is defined as generic superposition of energy eigenmodes

$$|\phi\rangle \equiv \sum_n a_n|\phi_n\rangle. \quad (59)$$

In this way we can represent cyclic fields in an Hilbert space. With this Hilbert notation the time evolution of a generic Hilbert state, as well as of a generic cyclic field, turns out to be described by the familiar Schrödinger equation

$$i\hbar\partial_t|\phi(x, t)\rangle = \mathcal{H}|\phi(x, t)\rangle. \quad (60)$$

As can be easily seen in the free case, *i.e.* homogeneous Hamiltonian (we will generalize later to interactions), the finite time evolution is given by the operator

$$\mathcal{U}(t; t_i) = e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar}\mathcal{H}(t-t_i)} \quad (61)$$

which turns out to be a Markovian operator:

$$\mathcal{U}(t_f; t_i) = \prod_{m=0}^{N-1} \mathcal{U}(t_i + t_{m+1}; t_i + t_m - \epsilon) \quad (62)$$

where $N\epsilon = t'' - t'$. Similarly considerations can be applied to the spatial evolution. The finite classical space-time evolution in the Schrödinger representation is

$$\begin{aligned} |\phi(t, \mathbf{x})\rangle &= \mathcal{U}(\mathbf{x}, t; 0, 0)|\phi\rangle = e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar}(\mathcal{H}t - \mathcal{P}\mathbf{x})}|\phi\rangle \\ &= \sum_n a_n e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar}P_n \cdot \mathbf{x}}|\phi_n\rangle. \end{aligned} \quad (63)$$

In order to allow an easy generalization of the following result to the case of interaction, we will be describing the finite space-time evolutions in terms of the infinitesimal space-time evolutions of the Markovian operator. In particular this will be useful in the interaction case where in every point a different inner product must be considered. As a result we will obtain the integral product $\int_{V_x} \mathcal{D}\mathbf{x}/V_x$.

All the elements necessary to build a FPI are already present in the theory without any further assumption than PBCs. In fact, we can plug the completeness relation of the energy eigenmodes in between the elementary time Markovian evolutions obtaining

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{Z} &= \int_{V_x} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{N-1} \frac{dx_m}{V_x} \right) U(x_f, t_f; x_{N-1}, t_{N-1}) \times \dots \\ &\times \dots \times U(x_2, t_2; x_1, t_1) U(x_1, t_1; x', t'). \end{aligned} \quad (64)$$

From the notation (63), the elementary space-time evolutions of a free system can be written as

$$\frac{U(x_{m+1}, t_{m+1}; x_m, t_m)}{V_x} = \langle\phi| e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar}(\mathcal{H}\Delta t_m - \mathcal{P}\Delta x_m)} |\phi\rangle \quad (65)$$

where $\Delta x_m = x_{m+1} - x_m$ and $\Delta t_m = t_{m+1} - t_m$. Thus, proceeding in a completely standard way we formally obtain the ordinary Feynman Path Integral (FPI) for the time-independent Hamiltonian (57),

$$\mathcal{Z} = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \int_{V_x} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{N-1} dx_m \right) \prod_{m=0}^{N-1} \langle\phi| e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar}(\mathcal{H}\Delta t_m - \mathcal{P}\Delta x_m)} |\phi\rangle. \quad (66)$$

This remarkable result has been obtained by using classical-relativistic mechanics and without any further assumption than intrinsic four-periodicity. As in the usual FPI formulation in phase-space we are assuming on-shell elementary space-time evolutions [32]. Though we started with homogeneous \mathcal{H} , this derivation, being based on elementary evolutions of a Markovian operator, can be generalized to the interacting case as we will see in sec.(V C 4).

Proceeding in complete analogy with the ordinary derivation of the FPI in configuration space we note that the infinitesimal products of (65) in (66) can be generically written in terms of the action of the corresponding classical particle

$$\mathcal{S}_{cl}(t_f, t_i) \equiv \int_{t_i}^{t_f} dt L_{cl} = \int_{t_i}^{t_f} dt (\mathcal{P}\dot{x} - \mathcal{H}) \quad (67)$$

Finally, by using the notation of the functional measure ($\int_{V_x} \mathcal{D}\mathbf{x} = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \int_{V_x} \prod_{m=1}^{N-1} \frac{dx_m}{V_x}$) [6], the FPI in (66)

can be written in the familiar form

$$\mathcal{Z} = \int_{V_x} \mathcal{D}x e^{\frac{i}{\hbar} \mathcal{S}_{cl}(t_f, t_i)}. \quad (68)$$

This important result can be intuitively interpreted by considering that a cyclic field has topology \mathbb{S}^1 . Indeed, for a field in such a cyclic geometry there is an infinite set of possible classical paths with different winding numbers linking every given initial and final configuration. Contrary to ordinary fields, a cyclic field can self-interfere and this is described by the ordinary FPI [1, 6].

We may also mention that, [1], by evaluating the expectation value of the observable $\partial_x F(x)$ associated with inner product (55) of our Hilbert space, integrating by parts, and considering that the boundary term vanishes because of the periodicity of spatial coordinate, we find

$$\langle \phi_f | \partial_x \mathcal{F}(x) | \phi_i \rangle = \frac{i}{\hbar} \langle \phi_f | \mathcal{P} \mathcal{F}(x) - \mathcal{F}(x) \mathcal{P} | \phi_i \rangle. \quad (69)$$

Finally, by assuming that the observable is a spatial coordinate, $\mathcal{F}(x) = x$ [32], the above equation for generic initial and final Hilbert states $|\phi_i\rangle$ and $|\phi_f\rangle$, is nothing but the commutation relation of ordinary QM: $[x, \mathcal{P}] = i\hbar$ — or more in general $[\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{P}] = i\hbar \partial_x \mathcal{F}$. With this result we have also checked the correspondence with canonical QM. The commutation relations can be regarded as *implicit* (and not *imposed*) in this theory. This is a consequence of the intrinsically cyclic nature of elementary particles [1] conjectured by de Broglie in 1924 [12], implicitly tested by 80 years of successes of QFT and indirectly observed in a recent experiment [14].

C. Semi-Classical interactions

In this section we want to generalize our geometrodynamical description of interaction to all the possible harmonic modes of the cyclic field. In this way we will find a formal correspondence with the ordinary FPI of interacting systems. (Feynman diagrams and perturbative calculations will be discussed elsewhere [33].)

We have already seen that the classical propagation of a free cyclic field is described by a FPI (66) written in terms of the Lagrangian of a corresponding free particle with mass M [1]. On the other hand, we have also seen that local transformations of variables induce *internal transformations* of field solutions that can be used to describe a gauge interaction. Next we will formally extend this correspondence to the quantum limit. In particular we will see that the propagation of the cyclic bosonic field - with all its harmonics - is described by the usual FPI and Scattering Matrix of an ordinary gauge interacting bosonic field. The the Lagrangian in FPI (66) will turn out to be the usual Lagrangian of classical electrodynamics of bosonic particles, (here we assume again three spatial dimensions \mathbf{x}).

1. Bohr-Sommerfeld quantization

The assumption of PBCs in field theory in compact 4D can be regarded as the quantization condition. It is easy to see that PBCs reproduce the Bohr-Sommerfeld (BS) quantization condition. Intuitively the BS condition is a periodicity condition because it says that the only possible orbits of the system are those with an integer number of cycles.

The correspondence with BS is immediate in the case of free fields, since it corresponds to a isochronous system $T'^{\mu}(x) = T'^{\mu}$ (the analogous of to the Galilean isochronism of the pendulum where the orbits at different energies have the same periodicity). The PBCs applied to the free cyclic field (53) give the following harmonic quantization condition of the phase of the fields

$$\oint dx \cdot p_n = \int^{T'^{\mu}} dx \cdot p_n = T \cdot p_n = nh. \quad (70)$$

This is nothing but the harmonic spectrum of the four-momentum obtained in (52). The quantization of a free field through PBCs is thus immediate because both the four-periodicity and four-momentum are homogeneous.

The interacting cyclic field $\Phi'(x)$ is a sum of eigenmodes with the same form of the fundamental mode (35),

$$\bar{\Phi}(x') = \sum_n \bar{N}_n e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar} \int^{x'^{\mu}} dx \cdot \bar{p}'_n(x)}. \quad (71)$$

The quantization of the spectrum of the cyclic interacting field in $x = X$ is given by the PBCs at $T'^{\mu}(X)$, *i.e.* $\Phi'(X) \equiv \Phi'(X + cT(X))$, which can be written as

$$e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar} \int^{T'^{\mu}(X)} dx \cdot p'_n(x)} = e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar} \oint_X dx \cdot p'_n(x)} = e^{-i2\pi n}. \quad (72)$$

The quantization condition in the interacting case is

$$\oint_X dx \cdot p'_n(x) = nh, \quad (73)$$

according to (12) and (70). This is nothing but the generalization of the BS quantization condition in 4D [34].

We now define a four-momentum operator $\mathcal{P}_\mu = \{\mathcal{H}/c, -\mathcal{P}_i\}$, and a number operator $\hat{n} |\phi_n\rangle \equiv n |\phi_n\rangle$. In the Hilbert space associated with this interacting system the non-homogeneous operator $\mathcal{P}'_\mu(x)$ can be obtained from the homogeneous one similarly to (12),

$$\mathcal{P}_\mu \rightarrow \mathcal{P}'_\mu(x) = e^a_\mu(x) \mathcal{P}_a. \quad (74)$$

In fact the quantization condition (73) of an interacting cyclic system can be expressed as

$$\oint_X dx \cdot \mathcal{P}'(x) = \hat{n} h. \quad (75)$$

Therefore the quantization of interacting cyclic field through PBCs can be also regarded as a generalization of the familiar BS quantization.

2. Dirac quantization and Symmetry Breaking

We now consider the specific case of gauge interaction. For the cyclic field solution $\Phi'(x)$ associated with the *minimal substitution* (27), the quantization condition (72) turns out to be

$$e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar} \oint_X dx \cdot [p_n - eA_n(x)]} = e^{-i2\pi n}. \quad (76)$$

As it can be seen from (70), in the case of pure gauge orbits $A_\mu(x) = \partial_\mu \theta(x)$, this condition leads to a quantization condition for the Wilson loop

$$\oint_X dx \cdot eA_n(x) = hn \quad (77)$$

Similarly to the Hamiltonian and momentum operator we define the operator $e\mathcal{A}$ such that

$$e\mathcal{A}|\phi_n\rangle \equiv eA_n|\phi_n\rangle. \quad (78)$$

In this case the assumption of PBCs reproduces formally quantization condition of a Dirac string [35] [36] [37]

$$\oint_X dx \cdot e\mathcal{A}(x) = \hat{n}h. \quad (79)$$

This result confirms the result of the related paper [38] where the Dirac quantization condition (79) has been obtained in an indirect way just by assuming time periodicity for an abelian gauge field. It has been used to interpret phenomenological aspects of superconductivity such as the quantization of the magnetic flux, the penetration length, the Meissner effect, the Josephson effect. In this description, according to [38, 39], superconductivity is a phenomenological consequence of the breaking of the electromagnetic gauge invariance $\mathbb{S}^1 \rightarrow \mathcal{Z}_2$. In fact, in a pure gauge, because of the PBCs on the matter field Φ , the phase of the gauge transformation (47) is periodic and defined modulo factor hn . This can be seen also from (79). Thus the ‘‘Goldstone’’ θ of the related gauge transformation can vary only by finite amounts and the electromagnetic gauge invariance \mathbb{S}^1 is broken to the subgroup \mathcal{Z}_2 — without involving a *vev*. Notice however that this breaking of the gauge invariance is a quantum effect since in the classical limit $\hbar \rightarrow 0$ the quantization condition (79) yields a non quantized spectrum. Thus, field theory in compact 4D not only provides a geometrodynamical description of the gauge invariance; PBCs provides also a mechanism of gauge symmetry breaking with interesting analogy with the ones typically used in XD Higgsless and Gauge-Unification models [40]

As discussed in sec.(IV D), the generalization of the quantization condition (79) to the case of a non-abelian gauge $SU_L(2) \otimes U_Y(1)$ is obtained through following substitution $e\mathcal{A}(x) \rightarrow g\mathcal{W}(x) + g'\mathcal{Y}(x)$. As noticed in [41], the resulting quantization condition for the neutral component

$$\oint_X dx \cdot [g\mathcal{W}(x) + g'\mathcal{Y}(x)] = \hat{n}h \quad (80)$$

could provide a realistic electroweak symmetry breaking mechanism which can be interpreted as induced by monopole condensations.

3. The Scattering Matrix

The Hilbert formalism (63) used to describe the evolution of a free field $\Phi(x)$ can be easily extended to interacting fields $\Phi'(x')$.

The transformation under local abelian (polarized) isometries reproduces ordinary gauge interaction for the fundamental mode. Similarly to (37), the corresponding transformation of a generic mode ϕ of a free cyclic field to an corresponding mode ϕ' of a gauge interacting cyclic field is described by the following internal transformation

$$\phi'(x) = e^{\frac{i\epsilon}{\hbar} \int^{x^\mu} dx \cdot A(x)} \phi(x). \quad (81)$$

This describes the variation of periodicity (*tuning*) of the generic mode ϕ' with respect the free mode ϕ , as a function of the generic gauge mode $A_\mu(x)$.

Thus, from the definitions of the Hilbert operator \mathcal{A} (78), we find that the *internal transformation* of the cyclic field corresponds to pass from the Schrödinger representation to the interaction representation of perturbation theory. In fact we find

$$\begin{aligned} |\phi'(x)\rangle &= e^{\frac{i}{\hbar} \int^{x^\mu} dx \cdot e\mathcal{A}} |\phi(x)\rangle \\ &= \sum_n \alpha_n e^{\frac{i}{\hbar} \int^{x^\mu} dx \cdot eA_n} |\phi_n(x)\rangle. \end{aligned} \quad (82)$$

Now we define a *tuning* operator, Hilbert analogous of the *parallel transport*, as

$$S(x) = e^{\frac{i}{\hbar} \int^{x^\mu} d^4x \cdot e\mathcal{A}}. \quad (83)$$

This is nothing but the ordinary *scattering matrix* of ordinary perturbation theory. In fact, it turns out to define formally the interaction term $\mathcal{L}_{int}(x)$ of the ordinary Lagrangian of classical electrodynamics

$$\begin{aligned} e \int^{x^\mu} dx^\mu A_\mu(x) &= e \int_{\tau_i^\mu}^{\tau_f^\mu} d\tau A_\mu(x) \mathcal{J}^\mu(x) \\ &= \int_{x_i}^{x_f} d^4x \mathcal{L}_{int}(x). \end{aligned} \quad (84)$$

In writing this equation we have explicitly written the integration region as $x^\mu = x_f^\mu - x_i^\mu$ (modulo periods) and we have defined a current $\mathcal{J}^\mu = dx^\mu / d\tau$.

From a formal point of view, such a representation of interaction for a cyclic field as variation of periodicity actually matches the ordinary interaction representation written in terms of the *scattering matrix* of ordinary QFT

$$|\phi'(x)\rangle = S(x)|\phi(x)\rangle. \quad (85)$$

It is important to note that, as in ordinary QFT, this interaction representation is formally sufficient to describe QED in terms of the Feynman diagrams.

4. Feynman Path Integral and Scalar QED

With this formalism at hand it is finally possible to describe the evolution of an cyclic field (including all its possible harmonics) under a given interaction scheme. We will find that its evolution will be formally described by the ordinary FPI of the corresponding quantum system. In the specific case of a cyclic field transforming under abelian polarized local isometries, the result will be the ordinary FPI of QED (for bosons).

The description of the FPI given in (66), being written in terms of elementary space-time evolutions, can be easily generalized to the non-interacting case. In case of interactions the four-momentum operator \mathcal{P}'_μ of (74) is non-homogeneous. Nevertheless, even in case of interactions the space-time evolutions are also Markovian. This can be seen for instance by considering the scattering matrix (83). In fact the time evolution in the interaction representation is described by the exponential operator $\mathbf{S}(t) = e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar} \int^t \mathcal{H}_{int}(t) dt}$. Thus, similarly to evolution of a free cyclic field (61), also the contribution associated to interactions is Markovian $\mathbf{S}(t + dt) = e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar} \mathcal{H}_{int}(t) dt}$. Hence, in case of interactions the evolution is Markovian: $\mathcal{U}'(t + dt; t) = e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar} \mathcal{H}'(t) dt}$. The generalization of the elementary space-time evolutions (65) of an interacting cyclic field in terms of the non-homogeneous four-momentum operator $\mathcal{P}'_\mu(x)$ is

$$\frac{\mathcal{U}'(\mathbf{x}_{m+1}, t_{m+1}; \mathbf{x}_m, t_m)}{V_{\mathbf{x}}} = \langle \phi | e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar} (\mathcal{H}' \Delta t_m - \mathcal{P}'_i \Delta x_m^i)} | \phi \rangle. \quad (86)$$

Another difference with respect to the free case is that interaction deforms point by point the completeness relation. That is, the integration volume $V_{\mathbf{x}}$ of the inner product (55) varies with $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{X}$: that is, $\int_{V'_{\mathbf{x}}(\mathbf{X})} d\mathbf{x}'(\mathbf{X})/V'_{\mathbf{x}}(\mathbf{X})$ (the number of period N' remains fixed). The Markovian evolution of our cyclic system allows us to write the the evolution in terms of elementary evolutions (86). This guarantees the possibility to use a different inner product at every point $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}_m$ of (64). Moreover, in order to avoid that in every point there is a different integration volume $\lambda'_{\mathbf{x}}(\mathbf{X})$, the integration region of the inner-product must be extended to a very large or infinite volume $V'_{\mathbf{x}}(\mathbf{X})$ (large or infinite number of periods N'), much bigger than the (finite) interaction region \mathcal{I} . In this way the volume $V'_{\mathbf{x}}(\mathbf{X})$, as well as the normalization of the field, is overall not affected by the local deformations: $V'_{\mathbf{x}}(\mathbf{X}) \cong V_{\mathbf{x}}$. Thus the correct mathematical tool to represent this non trivial evolution is actually the integral product $\int_{V_{\mathbf{x}}} \mathcal{D}\mathbf{x}$.

At this point, by following the same generic demonstration used in (66) (plugging the completeness relation in the elementary evolutions), we find formally the ordinary FPI in phase-space of an interacting particle

$$\mathcal{Z} = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \int_{V_{\mathbf{x}}} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{N-1} dx_m \right) \prod_{m=0}^{N-1} \langle \phi | e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar} (\mathcal{H}' \Delta t_m - \mathcal{P}'_i \Delta x_m^i)} | \phi \rangle. \quad (87)$$

Similarly to (67), it is possible to define a Lagrangian $L'_{cl} = \mathcal{P}'_i \dot{x}^i - \mathcal{H}'$. Since \mathcal{P}'_μ in (74) transforms as the four-momentum \vec{p}'_μ of the corresponding classical particle (12), this lagrangian defines formally the action $\mathcal{S}'_{cl}(t_f, t_i) \equiv \int_{t_i}^{t_f} dt L'_{cl}$ of the corresponding interacting classical particle — written in terms of operators. Thus the evolution of an interacting cyclic field is formally described by the ordinary FPI in configuration space associated with the interaction scheme,

$$\mathcal{Z} = \int_{V_{\mathbf{x}}} \mathcal{D}\mathbf{x} e^{\frac{i}{\hbar} \mathcal{S}'_{cl}(t_f, t_i)}. \quad (88)$$

Finally, from the analysis of the scattering matrix (84) we find that in the approximation of the local isometries investigated in this paper, the resulting evolution is formally given by the ordinary FPI of scalar QED. In fact the resulting Lagrangian associated with the action \mathcal{S}' in the exponential is formally the classical Lagrangian of a charged bosonic particle interacting electromagnetically: $\mathcal{L}'_{cl} = \mathcal{L}_{cl} + \mathcal{L}_{int}$. With this formal correspondence to the ordinary FPI formulation at hand we can invoke Feynman's saying that if "the same equations have the same solutions" [42]. Hence the assumption of intrinsic periodicity can in principle be used for a geometrodynamical semi-classical description QED.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Field theory in compact 4D represents the natural realization of the "periodic phenomenon" associated to every elementary particle, as conjectured by de Broglie in 1924 [11, 12]. It is at the base of the wave-particle duality, implicitly tested by 80 years of QFT and indirectly observed in a recent experiment [14] (Schrödinger used a similar assumption in his *zitterbewegung* model of the electron).

In this formalism the kinematical information of an interaction scheme is encoded in the relativistic geometrodynamics of the boundary of the theory — in a sort of holographic description. This description of interaction has shown remarkable relationships with the following fundamental approaches to interactions:

- the approach typical of classical-relativistic mechanics in which interaction is described in terms of retarded and local variations of four-momentum;
- the approach typically used in QM to describe systems in generic potentials in terms waves and BCs. The dynamical boundary of the theory reproduces the retarded and local variation of de Broglie four-periodicity and thus the local and retarded variation of four-momentum of an interacting quantum system;
- in GR, gravitational interaction can be described as variations of periodicity of reference clocks encoded in corresponding deformations of the under-

lying space-time coordinates. Similarly, in our description, deformations of the four-periodicity are described as deformations the compact 4D.

- the typical approach to interaction of gauge theory is obtained because the variations of field solution associated with the variations of the boundary of the theory defines an *internal transformations* which, in the approximation of the local isometries described in the paper, formally matches classical electrodynamics.

Indeed we have found that *gauge interaction can be derived from the invariance of the theory under local transformations of variables* (isomorphisms) as gravitational interaction can be derived by requiring invariance under diffeomorphisms. This must be regarded in the spirit of Weyl's or Kaluza's original proposal of a geometrodynamical description of gauge invariance.

On the other hand the assumption of PBCs (or similar BCs such as anti-PBCs, N-BCs, D-BCs) provides a semi-classical quantization condition for the fields. In fact the theory can be regarded as the relativistic generalization of the quantization of a "particle in a box". In this "geometric quantization" reproduces interesting correspondences between well established quantization methods:

- the canonical formulation of QM, arises from the fact that a cyclic field is naturally described by an Hilbert space, that it evolves according to the Schrödinger equation and its cyclic variables implicitly satisfy commutation relations;
- the Feynman Path Integral is obtained as the interference of the classical paths with different winding numbers associated with the intrinsically cyclic geometry of the fields in compact 4D [1, 6];
- The Bohr-Sommerfeld quantization condition is nothing but a periodicity condition. It simply states that the allowed orbits are those with an in-

teger number of cycles (close orbits) and can be described in terms of PBCs;

- the Dirac quantization condition is obtained as a result of the periodicity induced by the matter cyclic field on pure gauge transformations.
- the Scattering Matrix naturally describes the variations of periodicity between a free cyclic field (Schrödinger representation) and an interacting cyclic field (interaction representation).

Remarkably, field theory in cyclic 4D provides, without any further assumption than intrinsic periodicity, the possibility of a geometrodynamical and semi-classical description of scalar QED. To this list of well established quantization methods it should be added that, as shown in [16], the classical to quantum correspondence of the theory yields to an interesting parallelism with AdS/CFT. This is manifest when the dualism of cyclic fields to XD massless fields is considered.

Finally the description of gauge invariance in terms of local transformations of variables (in the approximations of the paper) is a geometrodynamical description which mimics the geometrodynamical description of gravitational interaction of GR. This aspect of the theory can be regarded as in the spirit of Kaluza's original proposal and will be investigated in future papers by using the dualism of the theory to a XD theory.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I would like to thank M. Reuter and E. Manrique for the fruitful discussions; M. Neubert, R. Volkas and T. Gherghetta for their interest in new ideas; N. Liu for the help in proofreading. This work is part of the project "*Compact Time and Determinism*" and it has been presented at QTS7 August 2011, Prague.

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